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Marketing Strategies of Ice Cream Companies in India

Dr. Saurabh Verma

Associate Professor, Department of Business Administration,
MJPRU Campus, Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh, India

Abstract

Although India is the world's largest milk and dairy products producer, it is surprising to see that ice cream consumption remains low at 400 ml. The Indian ice cream market is expected to grow to over 50% from 2019 to 2022, owing to several factors, including ice cream varieties available for the consumers, such as soft ice cream and hard ice cream.

The Indian ice cream market consists of both Indian and international brands. These brands are present across metropolitan cities, small towns, and even rural areas. While big brands account for a significant share of the market in cities, it is mostly the unorganised players contributing significantly to its growth in rural areas.

Keywords: marketing, Ice cream, companies, India, strategies, brands

Introduction

Maharashtra has the largest share of the Indian ice cream market. Uttar Pradesh and Gujarat are behind Maharashtra, capturing the second and third largest share, respectively. The most prominent Indian ice cream space players include the Gujarat Cooperative Milk Marketing Federation Limited (GCMMF), Kwality Walls, Mother Dairy, and Vadilal. Other factors, including ice-cream products like lactose-free ice creams and frozen desserts, can also be considered significant contributors to the Indian ice cream market's growth. Among these, frozen desserts have contributed mainly to the development of markets. By 2021, the Indian ice cream industry is expected to cross \$3.4 billion in revenue, making it one of the fastest-growing industries in the dairy sector.

Rural India has immense potential for the growth of the ice-cream markets. However, long power cuts during summer have made it harder to manufacture and sell ice cream products in villages. During summer, when there are power cuts, large quantities of ice cream melt away due to the heat. Since the cold storage logistics infrastructure is still developing in these parts of the country, power cuts make it harder to store and preserve ice creams.[1,2,3]

However, according to experts, the situation is changing drastically. Rural India accounts for 70 per cent of the total population. So, by developing ethnic flavours for this segment, coupled with diversification in packaging, and aiding ice cream vendors, both financially and otherwise, a host of opportunities is bound to spring up in these areas.

India has a tropical climate. So, no doubt setting up an ice cream parlour will **attract customers**, especially during summer.

There are many successful ways to market an ice cream brand in rural India. Here are some ways to promote your ice cream business.

According to brand design agency, the brand logo is the first face which represents your brand in front of the audience.

There are a lot of factors considered while designing brand logo design which can be from brand personality, target audience, brand story, positioning many more. There are tons of ice cream logo styles from modern to classic logos, kid-friendly to mature logos. Detailed to minimalist logos, this will differ as per above-said factors.

Classic ice cream logos as the name suggest are a very traditional way of incorporating your brand story, history and values. At the same time, the modern or urban brand logo is dynamic, progressive with simplistic font and make sure to be aligned as per the trend.

The modern and vibrant design is a must to make sure you attract kids. Abbreviation are a kind of great resource when it comes to designing a minimalist logo along with the creative image, which represents ice-cream.[4,5,6]

Brand strategy

Few trends which are included as a brand strategy in the ice-cream industry as below:

- Increase in disposable income of young Indians
- Increase the new flavours to keep the brand fresh and updated
- Understand the changing health-conscious pattern of Indian consumers and introduce health-conscious range (fat-free, low cream, vegetarian)
- Introduce deliveries and maximum processes with a minimum human touch to avoid the virus transmission risk.

Positioning

It is a process of creating space in the minds of customers and convincing them to purchase your product over the competition.

Positioning can be made secure by providing a strong brand message through taglines.

Example:

Amul has promoted its ice creams as a real ice-cream which were the healthy option and that they told us how health comes first along with taste keeping the prime importance. Amul is a brand which promotes being 'healthy' and 'value-for-money' at the same time.

Naturals Ice-creams they are known for providing ice-cream which is extracted from real fruits with no preservatives added hence called as naturals.

Baskin-Robins ice-creams are known to be costly due to their high quality and world-famous brand name; hence they position themselves in the premium category.

1. Host Contests

Whether cities or villages, everybody loves challenges. You could host a fun-filled ice cream eating contest by collaborating with local restaurants. You could also offer to give away prizes, such as hats, T-shirts, and other such branded memorabilia. The more fun and exciting these contests are, the more customers they will attract.[7,8,9]

2. Door-to-Door Selling

Contests can be an effective way to promote your ice cream brand. However, if you are still wondering how to attract customers, you can try to sell your products by going to your customer's doorsteps. Doing so will help you in many ways.

- You can get to know the area better in terms of its population and their preferences when it comes to ice cream.

- You can also learn the local language and communicate better with your consumers.
- You can boost sales with the help of public relations and by getting to know your customers.

3. Attend Local Fairs and Exhibitions

Most villages host fairs and exhibitions every now and then. These fairs and exhibitions can help you promote your ice cream brand. Since they are a form of entertainment for rural folks, you can offer them to try your ice cream brand on a hot summer day when the village hosts these fairs.

4. A Free Tasting Experience at a Local Grocery Store

To boost sales, another technique that you could try is to offer a free tasting experience at any of the local grocery stores. You could also do this yourself. That is, operate a tasting bar at the grocery store and offer your customers a chance to experience what your brand tastes like before it is released.

5. Price Cuts, Refunds, and Exchanges on Premium Collections

All customers, including the rural ones, love those Buy-1-Get-1-Free promotional offers. Similarly, they may also like price cuts on your premium collections or even cashback offers. So, you could offer price cuts and other attractive discounts that are bound to bring you more customers. Alternatively, you could also offer exchange premiums, wherein you could refund the money on new purchases your customers make in exchange for their old ones.

Ice cream is one of the most sought-after desserts in India, both in urban and rural areas. However, when it comes to marketing an ice cream brand, there are various ways in which you can promote your business in rural India, including hosting ice-cream eating contests, offering free tasting experiences, offering price cuts, refunds, exchanges, and other such promotions, and by attending local fairs and exhibitions.

DISCUSSION

Kamaths Ourtimes Icecreams Pvt Ltd (Natural Ice Cream) is a homegrown Indian brand that has been making waves in the ice cream industry for over 30 years. Founded in 1984 by Raghunandan Kamath, Naturals started out as a small ice cream parlor in Juhu, Mumbai. The company quickly gained popularity for its use of fresh, natural ingredients and its commitment to quality.[10,11,12]

Naturals' success can be attributed to a number of factors, including:

- A focus on quality: Naturals uses only the freshest, natural ingredients in its ice creams. The company sources its fruits and vegetables from local farmers, and it makes its own ice cream bases from scratch. This commitment to quality has helped Naturals to develop a loyal following of customers who appreciate the taste and texture of its ice cream.
- A commitment to innovation: Naturals is constantly innovating and introducing new flavors and products. The company has a team of in-house chefs who are always coming up with new ideas. This has helped Naturals to stay ahead of the competition and to appeal to a wide range of tastes.
- A strong marketing strategy: Naturals has a strong marketing strategy that has helped it to reach a wide audience. The company uses a variety of channels to promote its products, including television, print, and social media. This has helped Naturals to build brand awareness and to generate demand for its ice cream.

As a result of its success, Naturals has grown from a small ice cream parlor to a national brand with over 135 outlets across India. The company is also expanding into international markets, with plans to open stores in the Middle East and Southeast Asia.

Naturals Ice Cream is a success story that is inspiring entrepreneurs everywhere. The company's founder, Raghunandan Kamath, started out with a small investment and a big dream. He built his

business on the principles of quality, innovation, and marketing. As a result, Naturals has become one of the most popular ice cream brands in India.

If you are thinking about starting your own business, Naturals Ice Cream is a great example of what can be achieved with hard work, dedication, and a commitment to quality.[13,14,15]

Here are some tips for starting your own ice cream business:

- Do your research. Before you start any business, it is important to do your research and understand the industry you are getting into. This includes understanding the competition, the target market, and the costs involved in starting and running a business.
- Have a clear vision. What do you want your ice cream business to be? What kind of experience do you want to create for your customers? Having a clear vision will help you to stay focused and make decisions that are in line with your goals.
- Start small. It is not necessary to start with a large ice cream factory. You can start small by selling your ice cream at farmers' markets or local events. This will help you to test your product and to get feedback from customers.
- Focus on quality. Use fresh, natural ingredients and make your ice cream from scratch. This will help you to differentiate your business from the competition and to create a product that people will love.
- Market your business. Let people know about your ice cream business! Use social media, print advertising, and public relations to get the word out.

RESULTS

Even during the Ice Cream Congress and Expo this September, industry peers didn't realise the Chona family was literally freezing terms of their sale to South Korean giant Lotte Confectionary at eye-popping valuations. But within two months came that announcement, sending the entire trade into a tizzy.

Late November, Lotte scooped up Havmor, India's seventh largest ice cream brand, for Rs 1,020 crore in an all-cash deal, more importantly paying a multiple in excess of 2.5 times its 2016- 2017 turnover of 400 crore.

Marketing Strategy of Kquality Walls analyzes the brand with the marketing mix framework which covers the 4Ps (Product, Price, Place, Promotion). These business strategies, based on Kquality Walls marketing mix, help the brand succeed in the market. Let us start the Kquality Walls Marketing Strategy & Mix to understand its product, pricing, advertising & distribution strategies:

The product strategy and mix in Kquality Walls marketing strategy can be explained as follows:

Kquality Walls is a popular ice-cream manufactured by HUL in India. Kquality Walls is known for offering a wide array of frozen desserts in its marketing mix such as Ice creams and Kulfi. Kquality Walls also sells such popular brands such as Cornetto, Feast, Fruttare, Paddle Pop, Kulfeez, Cassata, Carte Dor, Creamy Delights and Magnum. Its ice creams offer delicious fruity and sweet flavours to suit the ever-evolving Indian taste palette.

Some of Kquality Walls' entry level ice creams include the kulfeez, which has a distinct creamy flavour resembling that of the very India 'kulfi'. Kquality Walls Cornetto is a cone ice cream with a solid block of chocolate at the bottom and a crusty top with almonds and other nuts. Kquality Walls Magnum being its flagship ice cream offers a Belgium flavour to its chocolate.[16,17,18]

Kquality Walls Price/Pricing Strategy:

Below is the pricing strategy in Kquality Walls marketing strategy:

Kwality Walls is a leader in the Indian segment but still faces stiff competition. The 200 crore ice cream brand continues to thrive in the market despite strict competition from Mother Dairy and Amul is because of its aggressive pricing strategy in its marketing mix.

Kwality Walls caters to a wide range of customers with varied pocket sizes. At an entry level its kulfi and small chocobar help it derive the volumes required for sustenance. While at the top of the frozen desserts line sits the Kwality Walls Magnum which is a distinct Belgian and truffle taste and therefore commands a premium in the market. Its ice creams start at a modest Rs 15 all the way upto Rs 80 for the discerning upmarket customer. The Kwality Walls Cornetto sits in the middle of the desserts range priced between Rs 20 and Rs 40. This enables it to capture a wide range of audience and dominate every market category they are present.

Kwality Walls Place & Distribution Strategy:

Following is the distribution strategy in the Kwality Walls marketing mix:

Kwality Walls produces and sells frozen desserts & ice-creams all over India as well as Bhutan, Nepal, Malaysia and Brunei. Kwality Walls benefits from its very widespread retail and distribution network. This helps it penetrate the Indian subcontinent with an ease none of its competitors can. Kwality Walls' wide distribution also helps it achieve economies of scale, thereby reducing costs of each ice cream sold through a reduction in logistics costs. Also its dealer margins are greater for remote and far flung places than in cities, providing an opportunity for even further expansion and penetration.

Kwality Walls ice-creams are available through a well established distribution system of HUL, and can easily be bought at grocery stores, supermarkets, restaurants, hotels etc.

Kwality Walls Promotion & Advertising Strategy:

The promotional and advertising strategy in the Kwality Walls marketing strategy is as follows:

Kwality Walls has and continues to use creative marketing and promotional strategies to further the brand name and message. As a part of its marketing mix strategy to advertise its brand, Kwality Walls uses all media like billboards, online, print media and TV commercials to create brand awareness. Kwality Walls has tied up with coupon companies online and gives out free or discount coupons for increased sales and promotion. By utilizing the popular appeal of actors such as Kareena Kapoor and by aggressively launching other ad campaigns over social media, Kwality Walls has ensured that its name continues to be synonymous with ice creams in India. By removing the word 'ice cream' from its ad campaigns, as directed by Hindustan Unilever's marketing experts it wants to be seen more as a cold desserts manufacturer than an out and out ice cream company, thereby making the selling umbrella broader and making space for the accommodation of new products in the coming years. Hence, this shows the marketing mix of Kwality Walls ice cream brand from HUL.[19]

About Kwality Walls:

A frozen desserts brand, Kwality Walls is owned by the consumer goods company of India, Hindustan Unilever. An amalgamated name made out of two separate companies that Unilever had acquired, Wall's of UK and Kwality of India. A major producer of ice creams and other frozen desserts, Kwality Walls is the most popular and one of the most respected brands. Founded in 1956, the original company from India was Kwality and it first imported machinery to mass produce ice cream commercially. Thereafter it was acquired by Unilever to form Kwality Walls as the umbrella name.

Nobody wants to miss out on enjoying ice cream on random occasions, gatherings, and even holidays, whether it's winter, summer, or monsoon. Ice cream is more of a preferred consumable, with high demand all year round but especially in the summer. Since India's dairy industry has developed a footing and the temperature is sweltering, the ice cream business can

be an attractive retail food venture. The younger generation's preference for eating outside is the key cause for the increased demand for ice cream shops.

Amidst intense competition and the launch of new brands nearly every month, the ice cream sector is doing exceptionally well. Because an ice cream store focuses on a particular type of food, the cost of the ingredients is comparatively inexpensive. Aside from that, ice cream shops are often small enterprises, thus compared to other restaurants, the cost of renting a space and covering utility costs may also be minimal

The ice cream industry is incredibly competitive. It is relatively simple to find ice cream-focused brands, fast food chains that provide the dessert, and individual vendors. Not every brand or up-and-coming ice cream business will likely dominate the market share.

You're on the correct track if you're considering opening an ice cream parlour business. According to a recent FICCI analysis, the market for frozen desserts and ice cream would reach a whopping 1 billion USD by 2022. The survey also demonstrates that the demand for ice cream in India is rising annually. Therefore, we can say with confidence that an ice cream store business strategy can be quite profitable if planned well.

In an ice cream shop, different customers have different needs. Some prefer the classic version without exotic flavours or new trends like nitrogen. While some customers might prefer a more exclusive experience. Regardless of current trends, creating a business plan for your ice cream parlour is crucial to help you identify the type of facility you want to create and the genre you are considering while keeping in mind your target demographic, location, and other crucial logistics.

This article will show you how to start an ice cream shop in India. If you want to know if an ice cream business plan is the best option for you, keep reading.

Step 1: Market Research

Launching a profitable ice cream business starts with careful market research. Ice creams are no longer considered a cheap delight offered from carts by local vendors. Ice creams are currently in the top tier of sweets. There is a huge market for upscale ice cream shops, unique flavours, and nutritious ice cream delights. You must grasp the potential of the neighbourhood market before creating an ice cream business plan. Conduct market research to learn about local consumers' expectations, the options currently on offer, and what's missing. Your business's path will become clearer as a result of this.

Step 2: Choose the Format of Business

There are different kinds of ice cream shops like small take-out-only kiosks at malls, on beaches, and in other heavily populated areas

takeout/sitting restaurants, or specialized or theme-based ice cream parlours. Choosing the ice cream business model is the first step. After you have assessed the format, the following step is to decide whether you wish to make ice cream and market it under your own name or choose a franchise model where you sell ice cream from a different company.

Step 3: Make a list of the products you want to sell.

You don't have to build a thorough menu at this point, but it's a good idea to have a general concept of the types of ice cream items for a shop that you want to sell. Ice cream is a broad term that covers a variety of flavours, including:

- Ice cream with real milk
- Slim-down ice cream
- Ice cream in prepackaged form

- Ice cream treats
- Frozen yogurt
- GelatosSorbets
- Cakes with ice cream
- Milkshakes with ice cream, etc.

After selecting your products, you can concentrate on other ice cream business ideas like store layout, marketing strategy, menu, etc.

Step 4: Determine Your Store's Location

In marketing lingo, ice cream is classified as an impulse purchase. As a result, people frequently buy ice cream on the spur of the moment. It is advantageous to have a store with a high footfall. People are probably tempted to make a purchase when they see others buying your product and enjoying it. Here are some ideas to have in mind while you look for a place for your ice cream shop:

- Optimum visibility to lure passersby.
- Look for stores that have sizable see-through glass to maximize the appeal.
- Ice cream shops do well in malls because of the constant foot traffic.
- A minimum of 400 to 500 square feet is required. If you want to set up a fancy café, you should look for parlours with at least 2500 to 3000 square feet.

Once more, the amount of space needed will depend on how your ice cream shop is set up. You will require additional space for the kitchen, cleaning spaces, etc. if you are creating ice cream in-house in a commercial kitchen.

Step 5: Purchase Equipment and Hire Employees

The machinery and ice cream shop equipment make up the bulk of an ice cream shop's investment. The franchiser will take care of all the equipment and machinery if you wish to open an ice cream shop under their ownership. The franchise fee includes the cost of the equipment.

You will need to buy the following items in this ice cream shop equipment list if you're starting your own brand:

- Industrial ice cream makers
- the deep freezer
- Refrigerators
- cabinets for storage
- cabinets for dipping ice cream
- packaging supplies
- plates and cutlery for serving
- chairs and tables
- a silent generator and UPS for constant power backup
- POS billing software

The following stage is to assemble your team. You will need to hire ice cream chefs, kitchen staff, serving crew, cleaners, etc. depending on the store style. Take a specialist ice cream-

making course to gain knowledge of the process's technicalities if you wish to manage the firm yourself.

Step 6: Plan Your Costing and Profit Margin

A reasonable ice cream parlour setup cost of the equipment needed for an ice cream shop includes a Cold Stone refrigerator (Rs 2-2.5 lakhs), a 500-litre chest refrigerator (Rs 40,000), storage cabinets and cutlery (Rs 30,000), raw ingredients and packaging (Rs 1-1.5 lakhs), and miscellaneous (Rs 50,000). Power backup is important for an ice cream shop because melting ice cream is the main source of waste in these businesses. Ice cream can be kept for two hours in a good refrigerator, but if there is a power outage that lasts for several hours, you are in trouble. So keep in mind to choose a top-notch quiet generator. This is available for less than Rs 1 lakh.

Since ice cream falls within the food category, all the permissions needed are relatively similar to those of a QSR: shop establishment licenses, FSSAI licenses, local municipal authority licenses, and fire licenses. A total of Rs 50,000 ice cream shop start-up costs are expected. To obtain the necessary permissions, it is usually advisable to seek out professional help. Since the process takes a lot of time, you can focus on other business-related tasks. Since ice cream is typically eaten as a dessert, the peak hour for ice cream sales is from 9 PM until midnight. To operate your ice cream shop until the wee hours of the morning, obtain the necessary licenses. The license Required are-

- Sales tax Registration
- FSSAI License
- GST Registration
- Firm Registration
- Business Pan Card
- Trade Mark & Trade License

How much of a profit margin should I maintain in my ice cream shop?

Ice cream should have a profit margin of between 30% and 40%, but this depends on your market as well. Consider that you have developed your own brand and are producing and marketing ice cream under this name. In that case, you must estimate making costs and other related expenses before calculating the profit margin. Your ice cream's selling price also depends on a number of other things. Your ice cream shop's profitability will be greatly impacted by its location.

The location is very important in increasing your revenues. The profit margin for franchise owners, that is, if you have accepted a franchise to sell another brand's ice cream, can be a little low because a specific proportion of the total sale amount is to be given to the main ice cream factory. The profit margin in the ice cream manufacturing industry will vary since each company will have a different cost of production, but on average it ranges from 15% to 35%. [16,17]

Step 7: Incorporate Selling Tactics

If you are thinking how to improve ice cream business, check out these smart selling tactics to increase your ice cream business revenues-

- Promote Your Store– Posting pictures of your delicious ice cream delights on Instagram and other social media apps is the most effective way to sell your ice cream parlour. The ideal strategy to attract ice cream lovers to you is to share your best pictures and urge your customers to leave reviews.

- **Offer discounts and deals**– Customers will swarm to your ice cream parlor in droves if you provide deals and discounts. You can provide discounts for children to encourage parents to spend more money on ice cream. A wonderful strategy to get rid of extra ice cream is to offer two-for-one deals or “happy hour” discounts on particular ice cream varieties.
- **Increase your sales volume**– Another excellent technique to boost ice cream store income is to sell ice cream by gallon or pint. People enjoy purchasing ice cream to store and eat later. You can sell it “off the cone” to boost ice cream sales.
- **Distribute samples**– Never underestimate the power of a free-tasting sample. Free samples draw a flurry of customers when offered. Once they’ve tasted the delectable pleasure of this creamy delight, many customers find it difficult to resist buying ice cream.

The Last Step: Opening Your Parlor to the Public

There you go. You have now mastered the fundamentals of starting an ice cream business. Just keep in mind that these are the basic rules. Along the journey, you’re likely to face further challenges. But keep going; concentrate on what you love. Always keep in mind your aspirations and the primary driver behind your decision to open an ice cream shop. Follow your heart, use your imagination, and open a unique ice cream shop that stands apart from the competition.

Personality

Brand personality of an ice-cream will be divided as per the below elements: Characteristics/Traits –Soft, tender, mature, classic, modern, rugged, sophisticated

Below are some examples as per their personality

Monkey stone brand is known for its robust and modern approach

Arun, Vadilal Ice-cream is known for its soft nature

Amul and Dinshaw’s is now classic yet with an urban approach

Quality walls are known for fun-loving youth and children

Baskin-Robbins is having a rich and inviting personality[15,16]

CONCLUSION

Ice Cream Packaging – Ice cream as a product needs no introduction; neither does it take much effort to convince someone to eat a scoop of ice cream. From being a luxury food item once, ice cream has today conquered the world. Due to the easy availability of affordable refrigerators, ice cream is easily available for consumers.

What a fun way to sell ice creams! This vendor in Turkey is also very famous on social media where people love to share their experience of buying ice cream with a few enjoyable tricks by him. This clearly indicates that selling ice cream in a highly competitive market is not as simple as it seems and also the fact that sellers can always find unique ways to entice ice cream buyers. However, not every seller or brand can arrange performances as the talented vendor did but every brand has a chance to entice the potential buyer with unique and innovative packaging.

Globally, India is one of the largest producers of ice cream and most of the ice cream is consumed domestically. Experimental ice cream products like vegan ice creams, ice cream cakes, Ice cream rolls, Ice cream sandwich (fritter) and more are have become popular too. But the aspect of ice cream packaging design has remained simple and unattractive. The selling techniques too have been limited to 1+1 or discount offers only.

Even though the ice-cream box packaging design is almost always very lively and colourful, this is not enough! Hence designing a product with creative and innovative packaging is essential to maintain the product on the market.

Ice-cream brand design with exclusive and outstanding packaging will make people buy it not only because it is good, but also because it looks beautiful on the shelf.

As per the brand positioning in the market, packaging design should speak for itself. If it is natural, organic, fat-free, from toned milk, vegan, whatever unique feature brand is providing should be mentioned creatively through images and content.

Tempting and mouth-watering images of ice-cream surrounded by ingredients will make ice-cream cone packaging design and family pack design should generate craving, which will then lead to impulse buying. The target group for ice-cream is majorly kids and youth; hence ice-creams should have a playful and joyful personality which will spread smiles and happiness.

If the brand personality is classic, then the colours will be very subtle, the content will involve more about legacy oriented data such as year of establishment, quality certifications and various branches nationally and internationally.

Ice-creams and kulfi are available in numerous flavours which can be from basic vanilla, strawberry, butterscotch, chocolate to gourmet oriented flavours blueberry, coffee, belgium chocolate and many more. Depending upon the flavours, the ice-cream box design, kulfi packaging design, colours, font, illustrations and content are based.[19]

REFERENCES

1. "Ice cream ad: HUL takes Amul to court - Times of India". The Times of India. 25 March 2017. Retrieved 21 June 2017.
2. "Dickie Dee men still pedalling bikes, ringing bells, selling treats". CBC News. August 3, 2015. Retrieved June 21, 2017.
3. Steele, Lauren (May 27, 2016). "An International Guide to Snacking". Men's Journal. Retrieved June 21, 2017.
4. Sheraton, Mimi (19 July 1978). "The Best Commercial Brands". The New York Times. "Ice Cream Labeling: What Does it all Mean?". International Foodservice Distributors Association. Archived from the original on 14 May 2008. Retrieved 9 August 2008.
5. "Ice Cream's Identity Crisis". The New York Times. 17 April 2013. Archived from the original on 2 January 2017. Retrieved 1 January 2017.
6. Farrokh, Dr Kaveh. "The Unknown Origins of Ice Cream in Ancient Iran". Dr. Kaveh Farrokh. Archived from the original on 4 February 2023. Retrieved 5 April 2023. The origins of the ice cream refreshment can be traced to ancient Iran where the technology to manufacture and store ice was invented as far back as 400 BCE or during the tenure of the Achaemenid Empire.
7. Book of Firsts. RW Press. ISBN 978-1-909284-29-6. c. 550–530 BC, First mention of flavoured snow or ice: during the Persian Empire
8. Marks, Gil (17 November 2010). Encyclopedia of Jewish Food. HMH. ISBN 978-0-544-18631-6. Archived from the original on 3 April 2023. Retrieved 13 February 2021.
9. Clarke, Chris (2004). Science of Ice Cream. Royal Society of chemistry. p. 4.
10. "Nice ice, baby: what's in those pricier Japanese shaved ice desserts". South China Morning Post. 18 August 2019. Archived from the original on 22 May 2020. Retrieved 8 April 2020.
11. "The Pillow Book". World History Encyclopedia. Archived from the original on 13 April 2021. Retrieved 8 April 2020.
12. Yako, Nao (26 September 2019). "Natural ice becoming popular source for shaved frozen treat". Honolulu Star-Advertiser. Archived from the original on 17 August 2022. Retrieved 9 April 2020.

13. Goldstein, Darra, ed. (2015). *The Oxford Companion to Sugar and Sweets*.
14. Weir, Caroline; Weir, Robin (2010). *Ice Creams, Sorbets & Gelati: The Definitive Guide*. p. 217.
15. Caroline Liddell, Robin Weir (15 July 1996), *Frozen Desserts: The Definitive Guide to Making Ice Creams, Ices, Sorbets, Gelati, and Other Frozen Delights*, Macmillan, 1996, ISBN 978-0-312-14343-5, Kulfi is the traditional Indian ice cream and has a strongly characteristic cooked-milk flavor and dense icy texture. [...] The basis of making kulfi is to reduce a large volume of milk down to a very small concentrated amount...
16. Day, Ivan (2009). *Cooking in Europe, 1650-1850*. Westport, Conn.: Greenwood Press. ISBN 978-0-313-34625-5. OCLC 428816114.
17. Weir, Caroline; Weir, Robin (2010). *Ice Creams, Sorbets & Gelati: The Definitive Guide*. p. 9.
18. Powell, Marilyn (2005). *Cool: The Story of Ice Cream*. Toronto: Penguin Canada. ISBN 978-0-14-305258-6. OCLC 59136553.

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